

	maximal shaft load $\frac{F_R}{2}$	$\frac{F_A}{2}$
LU086-3	356 N	68 N
LU086-4	392 N	75 N

$$\omega_{max} = 3,14,16 \text{ rad/s}$$

$$R_{pulley} = 0,024 \text{ m}$$

$$v_{max} = 7,15 \text{ m/s}$$

$$F_Z = \frac{m \cdot v^2}{R}$$

$$L = R \cdot \pi = 0,075 \text{ m}$$

$$m_{belt} = 0,075 \text{ m} \cdot 0,034 \text{ kg} = 0,0025 \text{ kg}$$

$$F_Z = \frac{m \cdot v^2}{R} = \frac{0,0025 \cdot 7,15^2}{0,024} = 6 \text{ N}$$

$$\text{Preload: } > (100 \text{ N} + 6 \text{ N}) = \underline{130 \text{ N}}$$